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THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK "FLOWERS PARADIGM" TO IMPROVE WRITING SKILLS

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Abstract. This article examines how weak writing abilities can negatively affect learners. What challenges do scholars encounter as a result of low-quality writing, such as unclear structure, limited vocabulary choice, and reduced academic performance. The paper outlines the theoretical framework of the Flowers Paradigm¹ by Dr. Betty S. Flowers, and some practical recommendations for elevating students' writing proficiency.

Key words: writing skills, structure, coherence, challenges, The Flowers Paradigm

Developing strong writing skills enables students to articulate thoughts with clarity, arrange arguments logically, demonstrate creativity, and participate fully in academic and professional context. However, a significant number of scholars state difficulties like lack of coherence, restricted vocabulary range, grammatical errors, and diminished confidence.¹⁹ As an example, essays or written exam assignments may receive lower grades due to ambiguous statements, confusion between formal and informal register, or inability to explain complex concepts. These challenges may hinder career success and potential opportunity to join international communities where advanced written communication is highly valued.²⁰

Within this validated framework, The Flowers Paradigm provides structured and effective model that guides learners through stages, offering an understanding about the writing process.²¹ The Flowers Paradigm was introduced in article by Dr. Betty S. Flowers in 1981, a scholar in rhetoric and writing studies, and later popularized by Bryan A. Garner. Dr. Flowers proposed this framework to present a step-by-step approach to the writing. Its main aim is to help writers produce clear, coherent, and well-organized texts while promoting personal voice. The Paradigm consists of four stages:

1. **The Madman Stage** - This stage involves brainstorming and generating multiple ideas without concern for organization
2. **The Architect Stage** - At this stage, the writer organizes the raw ideas and selects the main points in order to elaborate a coherent and logical flow. During this process, headings may be added to clarify key arguments.

¹⁹ <https://revues.acaref.net/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2025/01/20-TRAORE-SOUROU.pdf>

²⁰ Demneri, Ejona. (2024). Students' Difficulties in Writing in English Language. Proceedings of The International Conference on Modern Research in Education, Teaching and Learning. 3. 35-41. 10.33422/icmetl.v3i1.290.

²¹ https://open.substack.com/pub/impactfulspeaking/p/the-flowers-paradigm-a-comprehensive?utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web

3. **The Carpenter Stage** - This stage focuses on drafting the text by following the Architect's plan, ensuring connections between ideas and fully established paragraphs.
4. **The Judge Stage** - The final stage entails revising and refining the text, incorporating errors, rewording awkward sentences, and reworking sections to improve style and literacy.²²

In conclusion, enhancing writing is a multifaceted field that combines theoretical insights with consistent practice. By engaging in wide reading, daily writing, analyzing various writing styles, and implementing beneficial strategies, students can foster their writing competence, achieve greater educational progress, and play an active role in global communities.

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